

A Comparative Study to Assess the Level of Depression in Insulin Dependent and Non-Insulin Dependent Diabetic Patients Attending Medical OPDS at HSK Hospital and Research Center, Bagalkot

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ABSTRACT

Background: Depression is more common in people with diabetes than in the general population. Depression and diabetes are linked in a complex, bidirectional relationship. The exact cause is not known, but it may be due to combination of genetic, biological, and psychological factors. Depression can play a significant role in the lives of people with diabetes affecting their health, quality of life, and ability to manage their condition. Treating depression can improve the medical prognosis for people with diabetes. And diabetes self-management programs, and psychotherapy, especially cognitive behavioral therapy. **Purpose:** The aim of this study is to assess the depression level among insulin dependent and non insulin dependent Diabetic patients of studying in selected medical OPDs at HSK Hospital and Research center, Bagalkot. **Methods:** A comparative study with a sample 120 respondents of insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent diabetic patients age between 18-40 years & above was selected by disproportionate stratified random sampling technique. Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression scale was used statistical analysis. The data was entered in MS excel sheet and transferred to SPSS 25 for analysis. **Results.** Result of this study related to insulin dependent dependent diabetic patients and their level of depression shows that (98.3%) of insulin dependent had moderate level of depression, 1.6% insulin dependent had mild level of depression. Non-insulin dependent diabetic patients according to the depression shows (50%) were had mild level of depression, 41.6% of were had moderate level of depression and 8.3% were had sever level of depression. **Conclusions:** The study found there is an significant difference between Insulin dependent diabetic patients and Non-insulin dependent diabetic patients in their level of depression $P < 0.05$.

Keywords: Depression, insulin and non insulin, Dependent, Diabetic Patients, Medical OPDs and Hospital

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic condition that occurs when the body cannot use insulin. It is classified as type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus. The onset of type 1 and 2 diabetes mellitus is usually begin in childhood and adulthood respectively. It is believed that type 1 diabetes mellitus is caused by genetics, but environmental factors like viruses might trigger the disease. Type 2 diabetes mellitus is caused by several reasons including lifestyle factors and genes. ¹ Global health statistics estimate that depression is expected to be a leading cause of disability worldwide, and is a

significant contributor to the global burden of diseases, affecting about 350 million people. The World Health Organization (WHO) ranks depression as the fourth leading cause of disability worldwide and is projected that by the year 2030 will be the second leading cause of disability worldwide. Depression causes adverse complications to the affected individuals as well as society at large. Globally, it is estimated that the prevalence of depression ranges from 4.4 to 27.0%. It is higher among the population in middle and older age; females, low socioeconomic status, and poor social relationships. ² Depression, a common and often recurrent disorder has a number of risk factors which

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have been documented in the literature. Some of these include comorbidities with other conditions, other mental illnesses family history of depression and mental illness adverse events of childhood prior history of depression and treatment of depression and outcomes of treatment physical inactivity female gender, younger adults, smoking and having a chronic disease and unhealthy eating styles Depression is also a large burden on most economies and leads to increased mortality.³ Depression and diabetes are complex public health challenges, marked by the interplay of physiological, psychological, and social factors. The high prevalence and associated mortality rates of both conditions have drawn significant attention in recent years. Numerous studies suggest a bidirectional relationship between diabetes and depression, with individuals with diabetes being 2–3 times more likely to develop depression than the general population. Conversely, depression increases the risk of developing type 2 diabetes by approximately 60%. The comorbidity of depression and diabetes can impair self-management and reduce treatment adherence, potentially exacerbating each other and thereby increasing healthcare costs and placing a substantial burden on families and society.⁴ Type 2 diabetes is a chronic disease; individuals with diabetes are at risk of complications, such as, nephropathy, retinopathy, and cardiovascular complications. Additionally, a long duration of strict diet limit, glucose monitoring, and medication can cause psychological maladjustment, studies have shown depressive symptoms to be higher in individuals with diabetes and the prevalence goes up with disease duration and complications. Studies have shown the percentage of depressive symptoms in newly diagnosed diabetes.⁵

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the level of depression among insulin dependent patients
2. To assess the level of depression non-insulin dependent patients.
3. To compare the level of depression of insulin dependent patients and non-insulin dependent patients between the age group 18-40 and above years.

4. To find out the association between the level of depression of insulin dependent patients and their selected socio-demographic variables.
5. To find out the association between the level of depression of non-insulin dependent patients and their selected socio-demographic variables.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

METHODS

It was descriptive and comparative study with an intended to assess the level of depression among insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent patients among age between 18-40 years and above as perceived from the diabetic patients at attending medical OPDs HSK hospital was selected for the study.

Research Design and Participants

Study participants:

This study is a randomized controlled trial conducted in October 2024. A simple sample of 120 insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent diabetic patients from 18-40 years and above of age are attending medical OPDs HSK hospital in Bagalkot was selected for the study. Insulin and non-insulin diabetic patients were willing to participate in this study, and diabetic patients who were present at the time of data collection were also included in this study. diabetic patients who were not healthy at the time of data collection were excluded from the study.

Research Approach- This study aims to collect information about a diabetic patients and level of depression. Therefore, Followed proportionate stratified random sampling method was considered appropriate for the research.

Research Design- The term research design refers to the research plan. Research design is type of statistical analysis that helps researchers select subjects, identify variables, control variables, make observations, and interpret data. A proportionate stratified random sampling method will be used to select the sample from attending medical OPDs HSK hospital in Bagalkot.

Variables to Examine- A variable is something that can be measured and change something. The change

is the mental, physical, Quality of life, Hope, Characteristics and their personality. This study identified the changes.

Research variable 1: Level of Depression of Diabetic patients.

Socio-demographic variables- Socio-demographic variables included in this research age, gender, religion, educational status, Marital status, Occupational status, family monthly income, Area of residence, Type of diabetic mellitus, Family history of diabetics, Duration of Diagnosis, Treatment, Duration of insulin injection, Frequency of insulin injection, Type of device, Insulin Provider.

Setting of the study-The setting is where the population or the portion of it is located and where the study is carried out. The present study was conducted Medical OPDs at HSK Hospital and Research center, Bagalkot.

Sample and sample Size- This sample consists of subjects in the units that constitute the population of this study. The current sample consist of 120 insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent Diabetic patients age group between 18 to 40 and above years, attending Medical OPDs HSK Hospital and Research center, Bagalkot.

Sampling Technique- The sampling technique is selecting a portion of the population to obtain information about a problem. A stratified proportional random sampling technique was used in this study

Statistical Analysis- The data was analysed using SPSS version 25. The obtained data was entered in MS excel sheet. The obtained data were statistically examined in terms of the objectives of the study using inductive statistics. Frequencies and percentage was used for the analysis of demographic data. The mean and standard deviation, median and range was used as inferential statistics. The chi square test was used to determine association between level of depression scores and selected socio-demographic variables of insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent Diabetic patients. The chi-square (χ^2) test will be used to find out the association between the demographic variables with the insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent Diabetic patients

Ethical clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of BVVS Sajjalashree Institute of Nursing Sciences, Bagalkot.

INSTRUMENT

Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D)

The Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D Scale) developed by "Lauriesm S. Radloff" is used to measure the level of depression of insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent diabetic mellitus patients. Depression were scored with a total of 20 items as follows: 1: Rarely or none of the time (less than 1 day), 2: Some or a little of the time (1-2 days), 3: Occasionally or a moderate amount of the time (3-4 days), and 4: Most or all of the time (5-7 days). Diabetic mellitus patient's confidence in depression relations was created by the test-retest method ($r = 0.96$), showing that insulin dependent and non-insulin dependent patients are have equal level of depression.

Data collection process

Prior permission is obtained from the relevant organization before the data collection process begins. At the time the research was conducted, the diabetic mellitus patients were attending medical OPDs at HSK hospital. Data collection was conducted from all diabetic patients who met the inclusion criteria. Consent is obtained at diabetic patients. Before administering the survey, the purpose of the study was explained to the participants.

Data analysis

The obtained data were analyzed according to the research purposes using comparative and objective analysis. The main data was prepared based on the participants' responses. Demographic profile analysis with frequency and percentage. Mean and standard deviation of responses to questions Chi-square test was used to determine the relationship between level of depression in words and numbers and selected demographic variables.

RESULTS

Part I: Socio-demographic profile of Insulin dependent Diabetic patient. Sample characteristics.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-29 years	10	16.6
30-39 years	15	25
40 years & above	35	58.3
Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	45	75
Female	15	25
Transgender	00	00
Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Hindu	30	50
Muslim	20	33.3
Christian	10	16.6
Others	00	00
Educational status	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	10	16.6
Primary education	15	25
Secondary education	15	25
Graduation & Above	20	33.3
Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	10	16.6
Married	45	75
Divorced/sept/widow/widower	05	8.3
Occupational Status	Frequency	Percentage
House wife	26	43.3
Coolie	09	15
Employed	10	16.6
Self-employed	09	15
Agriculture	06	10
Family Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below-10,000/-	08	13.3
Rs 10,001-Rs 20,000/-	17	28.3
Rs-20,000/- & Above	35	58.3
Area of Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	31	51.6
Urban	29	48.3
Types of Diabetic Mellitus	Frequency	Percentage
Type-I	60	100
Type-II	00	00
Family History of Diabetics	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	23	38.3
No	37	61.6
Duration of Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 year	12	20
1-5 year	26	43.3
More than 5 years	22	36.6
Treatment	Frequency	Percentage
Only Insulin	26	43.3
Only Oral Hypoglycemic	24	40
Insulin with Oral Hypoglycemic	10	16.6
Duration of Insulin Injection	Frequency	Percentage

Less than 1 year	15	25
1-5 year	23	38.3
More than 5 years	22	36.6
Frequency of Insulin Injection	Frequency	Percentage
Once	16	26.6
Two times per day	24	40
Three times per day	16	26.6
Four Times and More	04	6.6
Types of Device	Frequency	Percentage
Syringe	35	58.3
Pen	18	30
Pump	07	11.6
Insulin Provider	Frequency	Percentage
Self	19	31.6
Spouse	17	28.3
Family member	24	40
Health care provider and others	00	00

Part II: Socio-demographic profile of Non-Insulin dependent Diabetic patient. Sample characteristics

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-29 years	12	20
30-39 years	18	30
40 years & above	30	50
Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	34	56.6
Female	26	43.3
Transgender	00	00
Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Hindu	38	63.3
Muslim	13	21.6
Christian	09	15
Others	00	00
Educational status	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	06	10
Primary education	09	15
Secondary education	23	38.3
Graduation & Above	22	36.6
Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	08	13.3
Married	45	75
Divorced/sept/widow/widower	07	11.6
Occupational Status	Frequency	Percentage
House wife	15	25
Coolie	04	6.6
Employed	15	25
Self-employed	18	30
Agriculture	08	13.3
Family Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below-10,000/-	10	16.6
Rs 10,001-Rs 20,000/-	17	28.3
Rs-20,000/- & Above	33	55

Area of Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	21	35
Urban	39	65
Types of Diabetic Mellitus	Frequency	Percentage
Type-I	00	00
Type-II	60	100
Family History of Diabetics	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	24	40
No	35	60
Duration of Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 year	15	25
1-5 year	26	43.3
More than 5 years	19	31.6
Treatment	Frequency	Percentage
Only Insulin	25	41
Only Oral Hypoglycemic	27	45
Insulin with Oral Hypoglycemic	08	13.3
Duration of Insulin Injection	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 year	12	20
1-5 year	20	33.3
More than 5 years	28	46.6
Frequency of Insulin Injection	Frequency	Percentage
Once	13	21.6
Two times per day	26	43.3
Three times per day	12	20
Four Times and More	09	15
Types of Device	Frequency	Percentage
Syringe	38	63.3
Pen	19	31.6
Pump	03	05
Insulin Provider	Frequency	Percentage
Self	19	31.6
Spouse	15	25
Family member	06	10
Health care provider and others	20	33.3

PART III: Frequency and Percentage of (Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression distribution of Insulin- Dependent Diabetic patient Scale) =60

Sl. No	Range of score	Single Child	Frequency	Percentage
1	0-20	Mild	01	1.6
2	21-40	Moderate	59	98.3
3	41 & above	Sever	00	00
			60	100

From above table the percentage distribution of Insulin- Dependent Diabetic patient and their level of Depression shows that (1.6%) of Insulin- Dependent Diabetic patient had mild level of depression, 98.3% Diabetic patient had moderate level of depression.

	Max score	Min score	Mean	SD	Mean %
Depression	80	20	49.7	0.76	31.60

Here, above table percentage distribution the mean is 49.6, Standard deviation is about 0.76 & Mean percentage is 31.60 of Insulin- Dependent Diabetic patient in this study.

PART IV: - Frequency and percentage distribution of Non-insulin dependent diabetic patient (Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale).

N=60

Sl. No	Range of score	Single Child	Frequency	Percentage
1	0-20	Mild	30	50
2	21-40	Moderate	25	41.6
3	41 & above	Sever	05	8.3
			60	100

The above table percentage distribution of Non-insulin dependent diabetic patient according to their level of Depression shows 50% of Non-insulin dependent diabetic patient were having mild level of

depression, 41.6% of Non-insulin dependent diabetic patient were having moderate level of depression and 8.3% Non-insulin dependent diabetic patient were having sever level of depression.

	Max score	Min score	Mean	SD	Mean %
Depression	80	20	26.18	0.88	32.72

Here, above table percentage distribution the mean is 26.18, Standard deviation is about 0.88 & Mean percentage is 32.72 of Non-Insulin- Dependent Diabetic patient in this study.

PART V: -Association between the Insulin-Dependent Diabetic patient with their selected socio-demographic variables

N=60

Sl. No	Socio-demographic variables	Df	Chi-square (X ²) value	p-value
1	Age	4	0.83	0.9344
2	Gender	4	0.31	0.9892
3	Religion	6	1.24	0.9749
4	Educational Status	6	3.05	0.8025
5	Marital Status	4	5.08	0.2792
6	Occupational Status	8	5.76	0.6741
7	Family Monthly Income	4	0.73	0.9476
8	Area of residence	2	1.16	0.5599
9	Type of Diabetic Miletus	2	0	1
10	Family History of Diabetic Miletus	2	1.64	0.4404
11	Duration of Diagnosis	4	1.33	0.8563
12	Duration of Insulin Injection	4	1.76	0.7798
13	Treatment	4	5.08	0.2792
14	Frequency of Insulin Injection	6	2.8	0.8335
15	Types of Device	4	0.73	0.9476
16	Insulin Provider	6	1.53	0.9575

***Significance at $\alpha = 0.05$**

PART VI: -Association between the Non-Insulin-Dependent Diabetic patient with their selected socio-demographic variables.

N=60

Sl. No	Socio-demographic variables	Df	Chi-square (X ²) value	p-value
1	Age	4	6.17	0.1868
2	Gender	2	1.65	0.4382
3	Religion	4	0.92	0.9217
4	Educational Status	6	9.08	0.1691
5	Marital Status	4	5.83	0.2122
6	Occupational Status	8	7.65	0.4684
7	Family Monthly Income	4	4.34	0.3619
8	Area of residence	2	4.53	0.1038
9	Type of Diabetic Miletus	2	0	1
10	Family History of Diabetic Miletus	2	1.01	0.6035
11	Duration of Diagnosis	4	5.83	0.2099
12	Duration of Insulin Injection	4	4.12	0.39
13	Treatment	4	10.96	0.027
14	Frequency of Insulin Injection	6	9.32	0.1564
15	Types of Device	4	3.37	0.4979
16	Insulin Provider	6	5.24	0.5134

*Significance at $\alpha = 0.05$

PART VII: -Comparison of Level of Depression between insulin dependent diabetic patient and Non-insulin dependent diabetic patient.

Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error	Mean Difference
Insulin Dependent Diabetic Patient	49.7	0.76	0.12	23.52
Non-insulin Dependent Diabetic patient	26.18	0.88		

As the data was normally distributed mean difference was used for comparison. The calculated of mean difference is 23.52. significant difference in level of depression of insulin dependent diabetic patient and non-insulin dependent diabetic patient.

DISCUSSION

In the present study comparative study was used, a similar study conducted by Tapash Roy, Cathy E Lloyd on assessment of depression the high rates of co-morbidity of depression and diabetes have been reported. The prevalence rate of depression is more than three-times higher in people with type 1 diabetes (12%, range 5.8-43.3% vs. 3.2%, range 2.7-11.4%) and nearly twice as high in people with type 2 diabetes (19.1%, range 6.5-33% vs. 10.7%, range 3.8-19.4%) compared to those without. Women with diabetes and also women without diabetes experience a higher prevalence of depression than men. Reviewed studies provide support for a modest relationship between diabetes and depressive symptoms, but the exact direction of this relationship remains unclear.⁶ The

present study is consistent and supported with the similar study was conducted by Anugraha, Aswini; Kantipudi et al, one hundred and fourteen patients (male = 36, female = 78) were screened for depression, and the diagnosis was confirmed with MINI. Twenty-six patients scored ≥ 10 scores, of which 8 (7%) met the criteria for moderate depression and 18 (15.8%) for mild depression. Eighty-eight (77.2%) had no depression. The characteristics significantly associated with depression were female gender, poor glycemic control, and systemic hypertension.⁷ The present study is consistent and supported with the similar study was conducted by Panel Mansoura Ismail, MaiHassan Seif, Nourhan Metwally, six hundred and eighty-three patients with Type 2 DM were enrolled in the current study. The majority were married (92.2%), two-thirds were males (61.1%), and almost half of them were Qatari and aged less than 50 years (48.8% and 48.2% respectively the prevalence of depression among patients with Type 2 DM was 20.1%, with the vast majority of them having mild depression (70.8%), while 4.7% and 1.2% had moderate and severe

depression respectively. The association between various sociodemographic characteristics and depression showed that depression was found to be statistically significantly higher among patients who were females ($p < 0.001$), married ($p = 0.018$), Qatari ($p < 0.001$), their age more than 50 years ($p = 0.013$), and with family history of diabetes ($p = 0.002$) 8 Our study results showed that the prevalence of depression was significantly higher in insulin dependent diabetic patient with 40 and above years of age (58.3%) compared to Non-insulin dependent diabetic patient age group 40 and above years (50%). In this study findings shows that the higher in Insulin dependent diabetic patient were moderate 98.3% has level of depression compared to non-insulin dependent diabetic patient were mild 50% has level of depression. The prevalence of depression in type 2 diabetes mellitus varied widely in different countries and studies. Zhang, Xu, Zhao et al studied 2500 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in China and showed that the rate of depression in this study was 5.7% (142/2500) according to BDI scores (BDI score ≥ 14). Stressful events could provoke and cause relapses of depression in both the general and diabetic population. Lee, Brazeal, Choiet al studied 421 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and revealed that the patients with stressful events had higher prevalence of depression than those who had no stressful events.9,10

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION:

The Insulin dependent diabetic patient; the percentage distribution of Insulin dependent and their level of depression shows that (98.3%) had moderate level of depression, were as (1.6%) insulin dependent Patient had mild level of depression. The non-insulin dependent diabetic patient; the distribution of non-insulin diabetic patient according to the level of depression shows (50%) had mild level of depression, were as (41.8%) had moderate level of depression, and only the (8.3%) of had sever level of depression, A similar study can be repeated in different regions of the states or nations so as to compare the results. The same study can be replicated on a large sample to generalize the findings. The study can be conducted by including additional demographic variables. More educational campaigns also should be conducted in their field. A true experimental study can be carried

out. A similar study can be recommended by using different method of teaching.

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SUGGESTION:

Health professionals can provide health education to young people everywhere.

CONFLICTS:

None

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